

Report on the Impact of Actors' Objectives and Power *Milestone MS 15*

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Methods.....	7
2.1	Research design.....	7
2.2	Data collection and analysis	7
2.2.1	Survey.....	7
2.2.2	Interviews.....	8
3	Results.....	9
3.1	Ethiopia	9
3.1.1	Introduction	9
3.1.2	Energy planning objectives	9
3.1.3	Power structures and networks in the energy planning landscape.....	11
3.1.4	Interest and involvement in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work	16
3.2	Zambia	17
3.2.1	Introduction	17
3.2.2	Energy planning objectives	17
3.2.3	Power structures and networks in the energy planning landscape.....	19
3.2.4	Interest and involvement in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work	23
4	Discussion and recommendations	23
4.1	Alignment with energy planning objectives	24
4.2	Perceived power and competence in energy planning	24
4.3	How respondents perceive the modelling work of RE-INTEGRATE.....	26
5	Literature	26

List of Figures

Figure 1. Primary and secondary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Ethiopia.....	10
Figure 2. Alignment of RE-INTEGRATE modelling efforts with primary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Ethiopia.	11
Figure 3. Network visualisation of the most important organisations for national energy planning in Ethiopia, based on survey responses. Arrows represent mentions by respondents (R01-R16), with size and thickness reflecting priority; more prominently mentioned organisations appear larger and more central.	12
Figure 4. Perceived power and competence of key organisations in national energy planning in Ethiopia. Power is based on a weighted count of how prominently organisations were mentioned by respondents; competence reflects the average of Likert-scale assessments. Each point represents one organisation, with labels indicating names.	15
Figure 5. Ratio between an organisation’s influence on and interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Ethiopia as perceived by respondents. Values >1 indicate that respondents assume higher influence than interest, values <1 indicate respondents assume higher interest than influence.	15
Figure 6. Respondent organisations’ level of interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling activities in Ethiopia.	16
Figure 7. Respondent organisations’ preferred modes of contribution to the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Ethiopia. Respondents were allowed to select several multiple-choice options.	16
Figure 8. Primary and secondary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Zambia.	18
Figure 9. Alignment of RE-INTEGRATE modelling efforts with primary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Zambia.	18
Figure 10. Network visualisation of the most important organisations for national energy planning in Zambia, based on survey responses. Arrows represent mentions by respondents (R01-R20; respondent R19 did not specify and is thus missing), with size and thickness reflecting priority; more prominently mentioned organisations appear larger and more central.	19
Figure 11. Perceived power and competence of key organisations in national energy planning in Zambia. Power is based on a weighted count of how prominently organisations were mentioned by respondents; competence reflects the average of Likert-scale assessments. Each point represents one organisation, with labels indicating names.	22
Figure 12. Ratio between an organisation’s influence on and interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Zambia as perceived by respondents. Values >1 indicate that respondents assume higher influence than interest, values <1 indicate respondents assume higher interest than influence.	22
Figure 13. Respondent organisations’ level of interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling activities in Zambia.	23
Figure 14. Respondent organisations’ preferred modes of contribution to the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Zambia. Respondents were allowed to select several multiple-choice options.	23

List of Tables

Table 1. Stakeholder Perceptions on the Power, Working Relationships, Competence, Influence, and Interest of Key Organisations for Energy Planning and Policymaking in Ethiopia.	13
Table 2. Stakeholder Perceptions on the Power, Working Relationships, Competence, Influence, and Interest of Key Organisations for Energy Planning and Policymaking in Zambia.	20

Glossary

AAU	Addis Ababa University (Ethiopia)	Mol	Ministry of Industry (Ethiopia)
ADRA	Adventist Development and Relief Agency	MoIHUD	Ministry of Infrastructure, Housing and Urban Development (Zambia)
CCG	Climate Compatible Growth project	MoLGRD	Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development (Zambia)
CEC	Copperbelt Energy Corporation (Zambia)	MoLNR	Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources (Zambia)
CEEC	Citizens Economic Empowerment Commission (Zambia)	MoLS	Ministry of Labor and Skills (Ethiopia)
CEEEZ	Center for Energy, Environment and Engineering Zambia	MoMMD	Ministry of Mines and Mineral Development (Zambia)
CIC	Chemical Industry Corporation (Ethiopia)	MoMP	Ministry of Mines and Petroleum (Ethiopia)
CIGZambia	Cities and Infrastructure for Growth Zambia	MoPD	Ministry of Planning and Development (Ethiopia)
DBE	Development Bank of Ethiopia	MoR	Ministry of Revenues (Ethiopia)
ECIC	Ethiopia Climate Innovation Center	MoT	Ministry of Transport (Ethiopia)
ECRC	Environment and Climate Research Center (Ethiopia)	MoTS	Ministry of Technology and Science (Zambia)
EEP	Ethiopian Electric Power	MoWDS	Ministry of Water Development and Sanitation (Zambia)
EEU	Ethiopian Electric Utility	MoWE	Ministry of Water and Energy (Ethiopia)
EFCCC	Environment, Forest and Climate Change Commission (Ethiopia)	NAZ	National Assembly of Zambia
EIC	Ethiopian Investment Commission	NGOCC	Non-governmental Gender Organisations' Coordinating Council (Zambia)
EIH	Ethiopian Investment Holdings	NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
EIZ	Engineering Institution of Zambia	NPC	National Planning Commission (Ethiopia)
EMPBC	Ethiopian Mineral, Petroleum and Bio-Fuel Corporation	PEA	Petroleum and Energy Authority (Ethiopia)
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency (Ethiopia)	PSI	Policy Studies Institute (Ethiopia)
ERB	Energy Regulation Board (Zambia)	REA	Rural Electrification Authority (Zambia)
ERC	Ethiopian Railways Corporation	REBs	Regional Energy Bureaus (Ethiopia)
ETA	Ethiopian Technology Authority	SAPP	Southern Africa Power Pool
EWiEn	Ethiopian Women in Energy	SIAZ	Solar Industry Association of Zambia
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations	UN-Habitat	United Nations Human Settlements Programme
GD	Gender Division (Zambia)	UNZA	University of Zambia
IDC	Industrial Development Corporation (Zambia)	WB	World Bank
IES	Institute of Ethiopian Standards	WRI	World Resources Institute
INDENI	INDENI Energy Company Limited (Zambia)	WSU	Wolaita Sodo University (Ethiopia)
KNBEPC	Kariba North Bank Extension Power Corporation (Zambia)	ZambeziRA	Zambezi River Authority (Zambia)
MoA	Ministry of Agriculture (Ethiopia)	ZARENA	Zambia Renewable Energy Association
MoCTI	Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry (Zambia)	ZBS	Zambia Bureau of Standards
MoE	Ministry of Energy (Zambia)	ZDA	Zambia Development Agency
MoF	Ministry of Finance (Ethiopia)	ZEMA	Zambia Environmental Management Agency
MoFNP	Ministry of Finance and National Planning (Zambia)	ZEMIA	Zambian Electric Mobility Innovation Alliance
MoGEE	Ministry of Green Economy and Environment (Zambia)	ZESCO	Zambia Electricity Supply Corporation Limited
MoH	Ministry of Health (Ethiopia)	ZRA	Zambia Revenue Authority

1 Introduction

Energy modelling has become an established practice for supporting decision-making in energy planning and policymaking (Pfenninger, Hawkes and Keirstead, 2014). The reliance on model-based evidence reflects a particular instance of the science-policy interface, a social process that connects researchers with other actors involved in policymaking, enabling the exchange, co-evolution, and joint construction of knowledge to inform and guide policy choices (Sarkki *et al.*, 2014). Techno-economic models typically are rooted in the belief in objectivity and universal truths, in line with the traditions of quantitative, evidence-based science (Bock and Pfenninger-Lee, 2025). However, using models to explore and reason about future developments requires a different mindset, stressing the acceptance of uncertainty, complexity, and the role of interpretation. Scientific knowledge, like technological systems, is deeply intertwined with social structures and practices, and both function as political forces that shape and are shaped by the societies in which they operate (Jasanoff, 2004). Accordingly, modelling is also not a neutral exercise; it is embedded within social contexts that shape how knowledge is produced and applied. All models are simplifications, and as such, they are unavoidably subjective (Sgouridis *et al.*, 2022) – someone must decide which factors to include in what way and which to leave out. Against this backdrop, participatory modelling as a method to better reflect multiple perspectives in model design and scenario development is slowly gaining traction (McGookin *et al.*, 2024). Yet, participatory approaches are not without challenges: group dynamics can influence the process, and achieving inclusive engagement across all stages of a modelling project remains difficult (Lloyd and Schweizer, 2014). Moreover, political influence can shape modelling efforts, as policymakers may steer narratives or outcomes to support pre-existing agendas (Süsser *et al.*, 2021).

In response to these dynamics, we developed task T5.2 to explore which actors are directly or indirectly involved in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work, and how they influence its trajectory:

T5.2 Impact of actors' objectives and power on model design and outputs (M01 – M24).

Lead: TUD. **Partners:** E3M, ENIT, UCB, SU.

Interactions at the science-policy interface, especially for the development of quantitative studies, often take place in a politically charged environment. The involved actors have specific objectives, interests, power, and resources at an organisational, sub-organisational, and personal level. These characteristics may influence a model's design, the data selection, and the definition of modelling assumptions and scenario design. With this in mind, the focus of the task lies in understanding the constellation of actors in depth to anticipate how the respective environment may influence the scientific outputs. Given the resource- and travel-intensity of the task, we focus again on the same two AU cases we zoomed into for T5.1, and we will extract lessons for replication of the approach in other cases. The understanding will be gained through field trips, interviews, surveys and workshops (the latter to be coordinated with T5.1 for efficiency). The insights will be shared with the other AU cases in the context of the scenario design and model choice and upgrade, to extract lessons learnt for these where possible and lay the ground for similar future analyses.

The two case studies to this end are the modelling work in Ethiopia, led by the College of Technology and Built Environment (former AAiT) at Addis Ababa University (AAU), and the modelling work in Zambia, carried out by the University of Zambia (UNZA). The main objective of this report is to inform and support them in refining modelling approaches and enhancing stakeholder engagement by focusing on relevant priorities and facilitating meaningful discussions.

In the following, we first illustrate our approach (Section 2) before presenting the results for the two cases, Ethiopia (Section 3.1) and Zambia (Section 3.2). We end with overarching conclusions and recommendations for the modelling teams in the two case study countries (Section 4).

2 Methods

2.1 Research design

Task 5.2 aims to understand how actor objectives and power dynamics evolve over the course of the project and shape modelling processes in the two case studies: Ethiopia and Zambia. Our initial research design envisioned the analysis of empirical data collected through field visits, stakeholder interviews, and workshops, using Ostrom’s Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) framework as the theoretical foundation (Ostrom, 2011). However, the launch of modelling activities in both countries was delayed due to external factors, and stakeholder dialogues only commenced in early 2025. In response, the respective modelling teams adopted a more ad hoc approach to stakeholder engagement, rather than continuous, in-depth involvement. These challenges, combined with constrained availability of local teams, led us to adjust the study design.

While the IAD Framework serves as a conceptual backdrop to this study, it is not applied in depth. Instead, the analysis provides a snapshot of stakeholder perspectives on the main objectives of energy planning, and on the power, competence, and interests of key actors in each country. These insights were gathered at the outset of stakeholder engagement, based primarily on survey responses from workshop participants and a small number of interviews with country team members. Although the scope was narrowed, the data offer relevant insights into how institutional roles, power dynamics, and technical capacity are perceived, supporting the ongoing development of models and scenarios both in Ethiopia and Zambia as well as for the further national cases.

2.2 Data collection and analysis

2.2.1 Survey

We developed a questionnaire specifically for this study, using the same set of questions in both countries to ensure comparability of results. Informed by Enserink et al.’s conceptual framework for actor analysis (Enserink, Bert *et al.*, 2022), we structured our questionnaire around three core themes:

1) Perception of Energy Planning Objectives

What are the main and secondary objectives of energy planning in each country? How do these align with the RE-INTEGRATE project activities?

The optimisation of total system costs remains a dominant approach in energy system modelling (Pfenninger, Hawkes and Keirstead, 2014; Lund *et al.*, 2017; Ringkjøb, Haugan and Solbrekke, 2018; Bock and Pfenninger-Lee, 2025). This applies also to the modelling frameworks used in our case studies: the main tool used in Ethiopia is OSeMOSYS (Salehu, 2024; AAU-1, 2025; AAU-2, 2025), and PyPSA-Earth in Zambia (Rajan *et al.*, 2025). The first section of the questionnaire focused on whether, and to what extent, stakeholders perceive the minimisation of total energy or electricity system costs as the main concern (multiple-choice), and what other objectives they consider important (multiple-choice, check all that apply). The suggested options were informed by existing research on energy planning objectives (Haydt, Leal and Dias, 2013; Lee and Leal, 2014; Ortiz and Leal, 2020). Beyond that, respondents could define their own primary and secondary objectives (option “Other”).

2) Perception of Power Structures and Networks

What are the most important actors involved in energy planning in each country? How do participants assess their competence, and their influence on as well as interest in the RE-INTEGRATE work?

To map the most important actors for energy planning and policymaking, the respondents were asked to list the up to eight organisations in their respective country they perceive to be most influential and rank them by power. In the analysis, we assigned a weight of 1 to the first-ranked organisation, 1/2 to the second-ranked, and so forth up the eighth-ranked organisation with a weight of 1/8.

In the following, respondents were invited to assess for each of the organisations they listed on a five-point Likert scale (a) how close their working relationship with the respective organisation is, (b) how they assess the relevant competence of the respective organisation, (c) to what degree they assume the respective organisation to be interested in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work, and (d) to what degree they assume the respective organisation to have influence on the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work.

3) Interest and Contributions

How interested are the respondents' organisations in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work, and how would they like to be involved in the activities?

Respondents were asked to rate their home organisation's interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work on a five-point Likert scale. While the format of an online survey is not adequate to assess the resources which the represented organisations are able and willing to contribute in-depth, we invited the participants to state how their home organisation would prefer to be involved in the efforts (multiple-choice, check all that apply). Accordingly, the intensity of their proposed engagement in the RE-INTEGRATE activities gives an indication of what type and degree of contribution the organisations are willing and able to commit to.

The surveys for both case studies were hosted online on Qualtrics and presented to the respective participants of the kick-off stakeholder workshops. Stakeholders accessed the surveys on their personal devices using a QR code or URL provided during the sessions. The workshop for the modelling work in **Ethiopia** was held in Addis Ababa on 25 February 2025, while the workshop for the **Zambia** case study took place in Lusaka on 3 and 4 March 2025.

The anonymised questionnaires and survey results are available on Zenodo (Bock, 2025).

2.2.2 Interviews

To complement the survey data and discuss the workshop experience, we conducted interviews with the RE-INTEGRATE team members in the case study countries. A semi-structured interview guide was developed to explore the team members' perspectives. In addition to taking stock of the team set-up and the approach to the modelling work, it covers the objectives of stakeholder participation, the workshop process and results, and the further stakeholder engagement process.

Both team members in **Ethiopia** were interviewed. The conversations took place online on 13 and 14 March 2025 in the form of Microsoft Teams video calls, each lasting approximately one hour. With the participants' consent, the interviews were recorded, transcribed, and processed into anonymised interview summaries.

The interview guide and anonymised summaries can be found on Zenodo (Bock, 2025).

For the case of **Zambia**, it was not possible to include interview material due to limitations in the engagement process.

3 Results

3.1 Ethiopia

3.1.1 Introduction

The survey was completed by 16 respondents, representing the following organisations (number of representatives per organisation in brackets):

- Addis Ababa University (AAU) (2)
- Adventist Development and Relief Agency (ADRA) (2)
- Ethiopian Technology Authority (ETA) (1)
- Ethiopian Women in Energy (EWiEn) (1)
- Ministry of Industry (MoI) (1)
- Ministry of Water and Energy (MoWE) (3)
- Petroleum and Energy Authority (PEA) (2)
- Policy Studies Institute (PSI) (1)
- Veritas Consulting (1)
- World Resources Institute (WRI) (1)
- Wolaita Sodo University (WSU) (1)

In addition to that, the following organisations were represented at the stakeholder workshop (Salehu, 2025):

- Ethiopian Electric Utility (EEU)
- Ethiopian Technology Institute
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)
- Manufacturing Industry Development Institute

3.1.2 Energy planning objectives

Almost 70 % of workshop participants consider the maximisation of electricity access in Ethiopia to be the most important objective of energy planning (see **Figure 1**). Considering that no more than 22 % of the population had grid-supplied access to electricity in 2024 (MoWE *et al.*, 2025), this does not come as a surprise. The most-referenced secondary objective is to minimise the environmental and health impacts of the energy system, followed by the optimisation of total energy system costs. All other proposed objectives were selected by less than half of the respondents, although they could check as many options as they liked.

Figure 1. Primary and secondary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Ethiopia.

The wish to minimise total system costs as a secondary objective of almost half of the stakeholders is directly aligned with the Ethiopian team’s main analysis tool, OSeMOSYS. At the same time, cost optimisation was mentioned by none of the respondents as a primary objective.

Yet, almost two thirds of those who prioritise a maximisation of electricity access believe that this goal is at least mostly aligned with the envisaged modelling work (see **Figure 2**). Given that the main focus of the RE-INTEGRATE modelling activities in Ethiopia will be on the decarbonisation of the transport sector (AAU-2, 2025; Salehu, 2025), this is surprising. While this perspective is not explicitly in conflict with the acceleration of electricity access in the country, it does suggest a prioritisation of electric energy for e-mobility. This reflects Ethiopia’s policy of promoting electric vehicles to improve energy security by cutting dependence on costly fuel imports and reducing climate impacts (MoWE *et al.*, 2025).

Although only three respondents selected system reliability as the main priority, it is noteworthy that two of them consider the alignment of this view with the RE-INTEGRATE work focus to be moderate at best.

Figure 2. Alignment of RE-INTEGRATE modelling efforts with primary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Ethiopia.

While there was the opportunity for respondents to define both primary and secondary energy planning objectives beyond the suggested options and highlight their personal priorities, none took advantage of this possibility.

3.1.3 Power structures and networks in the energy planning landscape

At least half of all survey participants mentioned six organisations as key actors in the Ethiopian energy planning landscape: the Ministry of Water and Energy (MoWE), the Ethiopian Electric Utility (EEU), Ethiopian Electric Power (EEP), the Petroleum and Energy Authority (PEA), the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and the Ministry of Finance (MoF). While the inclusion of the first four actors was expected, the relatively high ranking of the EPA and MoF warrants further consideration. Beyond that, it stands out that not all of these organisations were present at the stakeholder workshop: EEP, EPA, and MoF did not attend the event.

Figure 3 below illustrates the respondents’ assessment, centring around the often-mentioned and high-ranked organisations in the middle of the chart.

Figure 3. Network visualisation of the most important organisations for national energy planning in Ethiopia, based on survey responses. Arrows represent mentions by respondents (R01-R16), with size and thickness reflecting priority; more prominently mentioned organisations appear larger and more central.

Table 1 provides an overview of all the organisations which respondents consider to be important for energy planning in Ethiopia, of their working relationship with these organisations, their assessment of the organisations’ competence in this field, and the respondents’ estimate of how influential for and interested in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling efforts those key organisations might be.

With a total power score of 14.67, MoWE clearly leads the ranking and is considered the most influential actor by 14 out of 16 respondents. There is less agreement on the assessment of the following ranks among the survey participants. While EEU is ranked second based on a total power score of 4.68, it was assigned an average third rank only (average power score of 0.33) and is thus considered less influential than EEP and PEA across respondents.

At the same time, it is striking which organisations are not considered vital players by the workshop participants. Both NGOs and Development Partners¹ as well as Academia and research institutions are not perceived as influential actors in the energy planning ecosystem. The only specific academic institution that made the list is AAU (one mention), and, similarly, only one particular development partner was included, the World Bank (one mention), as well as one research institution (Policy Studies

¹ As both NGOs and Development Partners were listed by the survey respondents themselves, we do not know how the respective stakeholders interpret these terms. We must consider that there might be at least a partial overlap between the two terms.

Institute, one mention). While there remains significant potential for growth concerning the actual impact of academic and research organisations on energy planning in Ethiopia (AAU-2, 2025), the lack of acknowledgement of the significant influence of international organisations raises questions. Indeed, it is often international experts and consulting firms which are contracted for modelling assignments (AAU-2, 2025). For instance, the Ethiopian Energy Outlook 2025 was developed in cooperation between MoWE, EEP, EEU, PEA, and it received support by the Danish Energy Agency and the Royal Danish Embassy in Addis Ababa (MoWE *et al.*, 2025), and the development of the country’s Long-Term Low Emission and Climate Resilient Development Strategy (2020-2050) was led by Ministry of Planning and Development (MoPD) while receiving technical assistance from the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) as well as financial support by the Agence Française de Développement (AFD) (MoPD, 2023). The possible implications in terms of influence over the planning process, model calibration, and presentation of outcomes do not seem to be considered significant by the survey respondents.

Table 1. Stakeholder Perceptions on the Power, Working Relationships, Competence, Influence, and Interest of Key Organisations for Energy Planning and Policymaking in Ethiopia.

ID	Organisation	Power in Energy Planning and Policymaking ²		Closeness of Working Relationship ³		Energy Planning Competence ⁴		Influence on RE-INTEGRATE ⁵		Interest in RE-INTEGRATE ⁶		Influence/ Interest Ratio ⁷
		total ^{8,9}	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	
1	MoWE	14.67	0.92	58	4.46	67	4.79	67	4.79	68	4.86	0.99
2	EEU	4.68	0.33	49	3.77	60	4.62	55	4.58	53	4.42	1.04
3	EEP	4.25	0.43	34	3.78	50	5.00	44	4.89	43	4.78	1.02
4	PEA	4.37	0.36	41	3.73	34	4.25	49	4.45	51	4.64	0.96
5	EPA	2.16	0.24	36	4.00	32	4.00	35	4.38	35	4.38	1.00
6	MoF	1.76	0.22	25	3.57	26	3.71	33	4.71	26	3.71	1.27
7	Moi	1.37	0.34	16	4.00	11	3.67	13	4.33	15	3.75	0.87
8	AAU	1.00	1.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	1.00
9	MoPD	1.00	0.33	10	5.00	9	4.50	8	4.00	8	4.00	1.00
10	MoMP	0.78	0.26	7	2.33	10	3.33	11	3.67	5	2.50	2.20
11	NGOs	0.74	0.15	14	3.50	14	3.50	9	3.00	12	4.00	0.75
12	IES	0.54	0.18	7	3.50	9	4.50	9	4.50	10	5.00	0.90
13	Private sector	0.43	0.14	8	4.00	4	2.00	5	5.00	8	4.00	0.63
14	EIC	0.33	0.17	4	2.00	6	3.00	6	3.00	5	2.50	1.20
15	NPC	0.27	0.13	5	2.50	3	3.00	8	4.00	7	3.50	1.14
16	EMPBC	0.25	0.25	1	1.00	2	2.00	4	4.00	3	3.00	1.33
17	CIC	0.20	0.20	2	2.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	2	2.00	1.50
18	EIH	0.20	0.20	2	2.00	3	3.00	4	4.00	3	3.00	1.33
19	Ethio telecom	0.20	0.20	2	2.00	2	2.00	2	2.00	3	3.00	0.67

² Responses were weighted with 1,00 for the 1st-ranked; 0,50 for 2nd rank; 0,33 for 3rd rank; 0,25 for 4th rank; 0,20 for 5th rank; 0,17 for 6th rank; 0,14 for 7th rank; and 0,13 for 8th rank.

³ Likert responses were coded and weighted from 1 = “No direct collaboration” to 5 = “Very close collaboration”.

⁴ Likert responses were coded and weighted from 1 = “No competence” to 5 = “Great competence”.

⁵ Likert responses were coded and weighted from 1 = “No influence” to 5 = “Great influence”.

⁶ Likert responses were coded and weighted from 1 = “Not at all interested” to 5 = “Extremely interested”.

⁷ Total interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling efforts divided by total influence on the RE-INTEGRATE modelling efforts per organisation. A value above 1 suggests that the organisation’s influence is larger than its interest, and vice versa.

⁸ Weighted sum of the mentions of each organisation across all respondents.

⁹ The highest possible total for an organisation in Ethiopia is 16,00, i.e., all respondents mentioning the same organisation with first rank.

¹⁰ Average weighted assessment of each organisation among those respondents who mentioned the respective organisation.

ID	Organisation	Power in Energy Planning and Policymaking ²		Closeness of Working Relationship ³		Energy Planning Competence ⁴		Influence on RE-INTEGRATE ⁵		Interest in RE-INTEGRATE ⁶		Influence/ Interest Ratio ⁷
		total ^{8,9}	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	
20	MoH	0.20	0.20	3	3.00	5	5.00	4	4.00	5	5.00	0.80
21	MoT	0.17	0.17	5	5.00	3	3.00	4	4.00	4	4.00	1.00
22	DBE	0.14	0.14	1	1.00	2	2.00	1	1.00	1	1.00	1.00
23	Development partners	0.14	0.14	4	4.00	5	5.00	3	3.00	4	4.00	0.75
24	MoA	0.14	0.14	4	4.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	4	4.00	0.75
25	MoR	0.14	0.14	2	2.00	2	2.00	0	n/a	2	2.00	0.00
26	Academia	0.13	0.13	5	5.00	2	2.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	1.00
27	EFCCC	0.13	0.13	1	1.00	4	4.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	1.00
28	ERC	0.13	0.13	4	4.00	2	2.00	3	3.00	4	4.00	0.75
29	EWiEn	0.13	0.13	5	5.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	1.00
30	PSI	0.13	0.13	2	2.00	9	3.00	4	4.00	3	3.00	1.33
31	REBs	0.13	0.13	4	4.00	4	4.00	4	4.00	4	4.00	1.00
32	WB	0.13	0.13	3	3.00	5	5.00	4	4.00	4	4.00	1.00

In **Figure 4**, we map the stated organisations perceived power against the competence respondents assigned to them. The participants gave the key players MoWE, EEU, EEP, PEA, and EPA an average competence score above 4.0, suggesting that these organisations have at least considerable and up to great competence in the field of energy planning and policymaking in Ethiopia. It stands out that MoF and the Ministry of Industry (MoI), albeit among the top eight organisations in the overall ranking, have an average competence score of under 4.0. This suggests that they are considered important but not necessarily well-equipped for decision-making in this field. Similarly, the Ministry of Mines and Petroleum (MoMP) received an average score of 3.33. This finding could be an entry point for AAU to deepen the cooperation with important line ministries and offer their expertise in developing modelling and energy planning literacy among ministry staff.

Interestingly, NGOs, too, received an average competence rating of 3.5 only, implying that respondents consider them to have some to considerable, but far away from great energy planning competence. Development partners, while mentioned explicitly only by one respondent, were perceived to have much higher competences in this field (5.0).

Figure 4. Perceived power and competence of key organisations in national energy planning in Ethiopia. Power is based on a weighted count of how prominently organisations were mentioned by respondents; competence reflects the average of Likert-scale assessments. Each point represents one organisation, with labels indicating names.

In **Figure 5**, we illustrate the ratio between the listed organisations’ perceived influence on the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work and their assumed interest in those, based on the respondents’ opinions. A score close to 1.00, on or very close above or under the orange line, indicates that influence and interest are balanced for a given organisation.

Figure 5. Ratio between an organisation’s influence on and interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Ethiopia as perceived by respondents. Values >1 indicate that respondents assume higher influence than interest, values <1 indicate respondents assume higher interest than influence.

Here, it is noteworthy that key ministries (MoF, MoMP) are assumed to be significantly more influential than interested (ratios of 1.27 and even 2.20, respectively). This may lead the modelling team to consider the two potential stakeholder organisations as well as their roles not only regarding the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work but also energy planning in Ethiopia more broadly: what are their interests and priorities, and what might be potential advantages and risks of reflecting them in the model calibration and scenario design?

Further, NGOs and Development Partners are considered to be less influential than interested in RE-INTEGRATE activities. This is in line with the earlier finding that survey respondents overall consider them not to hold a decisive role in energy planning and policymaking in Ethiopia.

3.1.4 Interest and involvement in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work

Clearly, survey respondents consider the RE-INTEGRATE work to be of relevance, and over 80 % are very to extremely interested in staying involved (see **Figure 6**).

Figure 6. Respondent organisations' level of interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling activities in Ethiopia.

And the stakeholders show themselves ready to commit time and resources to the endeavour: half of the respondents would like to be directly involved in the modelling work, the most intensive way of contribution (see **Figure 7**). Further, about one third of participants, respectively, are eager to be consulted on the overall work and results, to provide data, and to influence the design of scenarios. Only about 20 % selected the least intensive mode of contribution, to merely be informed on the work and results.

Figure 7. Respondent organisations' preferred modes of contribution to the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Ethiopia. Respondents were allowed to select several multiple-choice options.

3.2 Zambia

3.2.1 Introduction

A total of 20 respondents out of 38 workshop participants completed the survey, representing the following organisations (number of representatives per organisation in brackets):

- Cities and Infrastructure for Growth Zambia (CIG Zambia) (2)
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (1)
- Ministry of Energy (MoE) (2)
- Ministry of Technology and Science (MoTS) (1)
- University of Zambia (UNZA) (9)
- Zambia Network of the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) Programme (1)
- Zambian Electric Mobility Innovation Alliance (ZEMIA) (3)
- Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA) (1)

It is worth emphasising that nine out of the 20 participants – representing 45 % of all respondents – are affiliated with UNZA, the institution responsible for carrying out the modelling activities.

Represented organisations beyond those who completed the survey included the following (Rajan *et al.*, 2025):

- Copperbelt University
- Energy Regulation Board (ERB)
- Ministry of Green Economy and Environment (MoGEE)
- Rural Electrification Authority (REA)
- Zambia Electricity Supply Corporation Limited (ZESCO)

Beyond the modelling activities undertaken through RE-INTEGRATE, several other energy-related modelling initiatives are ongoing in Zambia. Notably, the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) project is among them, with the University of Zambia (UNZA) also serving as a key national partner. When survey respondents were asked which modelling projects or activities in Zambia they were involved in – either directly or as stakeholders – only two cited RE-INTEGRATE, while six mentioned CCG, and five indicated involvement in other initiatives. This suggests that many stakeholders are not yet familiar with the work being done under RE-INTEGRATE and, as a result, do not see themselves as closely connected to it.

3.2.2 Energy planning objectives

Compared to the survey respondents in Ethiopia, the stakeholders in Zambia show less agreement on the primary objective which energy planning should work towards: 30 % prioritise electrification, while 25 %, respectively, consider the minimisation of climate impacts and the maximisation of energy affordability to be the most important goals (see **Figure 8**).

Additionally, respondents suggested to minimise “the impacts of climate change on various interdependent sectors” as well as to maximise “the security of energy supply” as primary objectives (free-text suggestions linked to the multiple-choice option “Other”).

Figure 8. Primary and secondary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Zambia.

Considering both primary and secondary energy planning objectives, 70% of respondents believe that the minimisation of climate impacts related to the energy system is a vital and thus the overall highest-ranked goal, followed by the maximisation of electricity access as well as supply security.

The minimisation of total system cost, reflecting the objective function of many capacity expansion modelling tools, is named a secondary objective by 7 out of 20 respondents, making it the lowest priority among the provided options. While cost-optimisation today is a widespread approach to energy system modelling, it may not be aligned with stakeholder and user preferences. This important finding might foster further discussion within the UNZA modelling team and the modelling community more broadly, including on whether better-suited modelling approaches are needed which consider energy panning from a different perspective.

Figure 9. Alignment of RE-INTEGRATE modelling efforts with primary energy planning objectives of stakeholder workshop participants in Zambia.

While MoE tops the list with a total power score of 16.67, there is less agreement than in the case of Ethiopia and only 75 % of survey participants consider it the most important organisation. While MoFNP is only the fourth-ranked actor according to total power score, the ten respondents who listed the ministry perceive it on average to be the second most important played (average power score of 0.41) – a striking result as finance ministries typically do not play a prominent and direct role in energy planning.

Similar to the case of Ethiopia, it stands out that neither development partners nor academic institutions are seen as crucial actors in the energy planning ecosystem. Development Partners as a generic umbrella term was listed by only one respondent, and the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) project, the Cities and Infrastructure for Growth Zambia programme (CIGZambia), and UN-Habitat were mentioned directly – but even CCG and CIGZambia, the higher-ranking organisations, made the list of only three and two survey participants, respectively. And this despite the fact that, as in Ethiopia, important policies and the underlying models and scenarios are supported and thus significantly influenced by international actors. The country’s Integrated Resource Plan for the Power Sector, for instance, was funded by UK International Development from the UK government and developed jointly by MoE with support from CIGZambia, implemented by the consulting firm Cowater International (MoE, 2023). That this engagement may imply a high degree of power and influence of those international actors over the planning processes and results does not appear to be considered noteworthy by the stakeholders.

While only three respondents listed Academia as a generic term for organisations of high influence, UNZA specifically is considered an influential organisation by 25 % of respondents – albeit mostly on lower ranks.

Table 2. Stakeholder Perceptions on the Power, Working Relationships, Competence, Influence, and Interest of Key Organisations for Energy Planning and Policymaking in Zambia.

ID	Organisation	Power in Energy Planning and Policymaking ²		Closeness of Working Relationship ³		Energy Planning Competence ⁴		Influence on RE-INTEGRATE ⁵		Interest in RE-INTEGRATE ⁶		Influence/ Interest Ratio ⁷
		total ^{8,11}	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	
1	MoE	16.67	0.88	74	4.11	81	4.50	81	4.76	84	4.67	0.96
2	ZESCO	5.74	0.38	54	3.86	60	4.29	63	4.50	59	4.21	1.07
3	ERB	5.27	0.38	42	3.50	62	4.43	59	4.54	57	4.38	1.04
4	MoFNP	4.14	0.41	35	3.50	36	3.60	44	4.40	38	3.80	1.16
5	MoGEE	3.53	0.32	49	4.45	48	4.36	50	4.55	50	4.55	1.00
6	REA	2.16	0.20	35	3.89	47	4.27	45	4.50	46	4.60	0.98
7	NAZ	1.00	1.00	0	n/a	3	3.00	1	1.00	5	5.00	0.20
8	UNZA	1.00	0.20	23	4.60	25	5.00	24	4.80	25	5.00	0.96
9	CEC	0.90	0.23	13	3.25	15	3.75	13	4.33	12	4.00	1.08
10	Academia	0.73	0.24	9	4.50	8	4.00	8	4.00	15	5.00	0.53
11	CCG	0.64	0.21	15	5.00	14	4.67	13	4.33	14	4.67	0.93
12	Private sector	0.57	0.19	9	3.00	11	3.67	8	4.00	14	4.67	0.57
13	MoiHUD	0.54	0.18	11	3.67	11	3.67	13	4.33	14	4.67	0.93
14	CIGZambia	0.50	0.25	8	4.00	9	4.50	8	4.00	9	4.50	0.89
15	MoTS	0.45	0.23	6	3.00	9	4.50	10	5.00	9	4.50	1.11
16	ZBS	0.39	0.20	4	4.00	8	4.00	5	2.50	8	4.00	0.63

¹¹ The highest possible total for an organisation in Zambia is 20.00, i.e., all respondents mentioning the same organisation with first rank.

ID	Organisation	Power in Energy Planning and Policymaking ²		Closeness of Working Relationship ³		Energy Planning Competence ⁴		Influence on RE-INTEGRATE ⁵		Interest in RE-INTEGRATE ⁶		Influence/ Interest Ratio ⁷
		total ^{8,11}	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	total ⁸	average ¹⁰	
17	ZDA	0.34	0.17	4	2.00	7	3.50	8	4.00	9	4.50	0.89
18	MoLGRD	0.33	0.16	6	3.00	7	3.50	8	4.00	9	4.50	0.89
19	ZambeziRA	0.33	0.17	7	3.50	10	5.00	9	4.50	10	5.00	0.90
20	MoMMD	0.31	0.15	5	2.50	7	3.50	8	4.00	6	3.00	1.33
21	SIAZ	0.27	0.13	7	3.50	8	4.00	9	4.50	8	4.00	1.13
22	CEEEZ	0.25	0.13	10	5.00	8	4.00	9	4.50	10	5.00	0.90
23	MoCTI	0.25	0.25	5	5.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	1.00
24	EIZ	0.20	0.20	4	4.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	1.00
25	ZARENA	0.20	0.20	4	4.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	4	4.00	1.25
26	ZEMA	0.20	0.20	5	5.00	4	4.00	5	5.00	4	4.00	1.25
27	CEEC	0.17	0.17	3	3.00	5	5.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	1.00
28	GD	0.17	0.17	5	5.00	4	4.00	5	5.00	4	4.00	1.25
29	UN-Habitat	0.17	0.17	4	4.00	4	4.00	4	4.00	4	4.00	1.00
30	IDC	0.14	0.14	3	3.00	4	4.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	1.00
31	INDENI	0.14	0.14	2	2.00	2	2.00	2	2.00	2	2.00	1.00
32	NGOCC	0.14	0.14	5	5.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	4	4.00	1.25
33	Development partners	0.13	0.13	2	2.00	3	3.00	4	4.00	2	2.00	2.00
34	KNBEPC	0.13	0.13	0	n/a	5	5.00	3	3.00	5	5.00	0.60
35	MoLNR	0.13	0.13	3	3.00	2	2.00	4	4.00	3	3.00	1.33
36	MoWDS	0.13	0.13	4	4.00	3	3.00	3	3.00	2	2.00	1.50
37	SAPP	0.13	0.13	4	4.00	5	5.00	5	5.00	3	3.00	1.67

Figure 11 shows the perceived power of the listed organisation mapped against their energy planning and policymaking competence as perceived by the respondents. Five out of the six highest-ranked organisations are assumed to have at least considerable competence in this field. MoFNP, however, stands out, and stakeholders assign an average competence score of 3.5 to it, implying a competence level between “some” and “considerable” competence. This is a parallel to the observation made in Ethiopia and, again, indicates that they are seen as important actors, though not necessarily well-prepared or sufficiently equipped to make informed decisions in this area. Here, UNZA might consider providing capacity development support to strengthen the connection to the finance ministry.

While Development Partners are assumed to have only “some” competence and Academia is ranked as having “considerable” competence, the two most highly regarded support programmes in the country – CCG and CIGZambia – fare better, and respondents believe them to have considerable to great competence.

Figure 11. Perceived power and competence of key organisations in national energy planning in Zambia. Power is based on a weighted count of how prominently organisations were mentioned by respondents; competence reflects the average of Likert-scale assessments. Each point represents one organisation, with labels indicating names.

Figure 12 shows the ratio between the perceived influence of the listed organisations on the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work and their assumed level of interest, as reported by respondents. A score near 1.00 – represented by the orange line – suggests a balance between an organisation’s influence and its interest in the modelling process.

Figure 12. Ratio between an organisation’s influence on and interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Zambia as perceived by respondents. Values >1 indicate that respondents assume higher influence than interest, values <1 indicate respondents assume higher interest than influence.

At first glance, a few apparent outliers can be seen; however, closer examination reveals these to be minor – for instance, the ratio of 2.0 for development partners is based on a single response. More notably, academia is generally perceived as having significantly less influence relative to its level of interest, with a ratio of just 0.53. While the ratio for CCG – the highest-ranked programme – is balanced, CIGZambia is perceived as having more interest in the modelling work than actual influence.

3.2.4 Interest and involvement in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work

With 75 % of all respondents being at least very interested in the RE-INTEGRATE work (see **Figure 13**), these modelling efforts are perceived to play a potentially significant role for energy planning in Zambia.

Figure 13. Respondent organisations' level of interest in the RE-INTEGRATE modelling activities in Zambia.

In Zambia, the readiness to commit time and resources to be involved in the RE-INTEGRATE efforts overall seems lower (see **Figure 14**). Only 35 % of survey participants wish to be directly involved in the modelling work. The most desirable option for respondents is to be able to influence scenario designs – immediately followed by the lowest-effort option we suggested: to be informed about the work progress and results without any direct engagement in the process.

Figure 14. Respondent organisations' preferred modes of contribution to the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work in Zambia. Respondents were allowed to select several multiple-choice options.

4 Discussion and recommendations

Based on surveys conducted during workshops in Ethiopia and Zambia, we examined how participating stakeholders perceive the most important primary and secondary objectives for energy planning in their countries. The survey also explored which organisations are viewed as the most influential and competent in the field of energy planning and policymaking, as well as the extent and nature of the respondents' interest in contributing to the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work. While these results represent a snapshot from the initial stakeholder workshops in Ethiopia and Zambia – and the limited number of survey responses cannot be considered representative of the entire energy sector –

the insights gathered still offer valuable guidance for shaping the ongoing modelling work of the AAU and UNZA teams and for refining their stakeholder engagement strategies.

In the following sections, we present the findings and draw conclusions relevant to the AAU and UNZA modelling teams. These insights can help refine their stakeholder engagement strategies and enhance their influence within national energy planning processes.

4.1 Alignment with energy planning objectives

None of the stakeholders in either country identified the minimisation of total system cost as the primary objective that energy planning should pursue. Nevertheless, the modelling frameworks applied – OSeMOSYS in Ethiopia and PyPSA-Earth in Zambia – are based on optimisation approaches, with cost-optimal solutions at the core of the analysis. Although this is not necessarily problematic in itself, the finding is cause for concern. Of course, cost optimisation remains a dominant and widely recognised method in energy system modelling, and both frameworks are well-established within the field. While a broader shift in thinking about the role of optimisation in long-term scenario development may be warranted, such a transformation lies beyond the scope of the current modelling efforts. Yet, this disconnect between stakeholder priorities and modelling assumptions raises important questions, as stakeholders may not always fully understand or reflect on what total system cost minimisation implies for the results they are interpreting. In any case, the finding presents an opportunity to engage stakeholders in critical reflection on the role of models and scenarios, including their benefits, limitations, and explanatory power. Facilitating this kind of dialogue can help strengthen the relationship between modellers and decision-makers, ultimately improving both modelling literacy and communication at the science-policy interface.

In both countries, stakeholders identify increasing the electrification rate as a primary objective of energy planning. In Zambia, respondents additionally highlight the importance of making energy supply more affordable and reducing climate impacts. While these priorities may not lie at the core of the current RE-INTEGRATE modelling work, it should not be the ambition to focus exclusively on narrowly defined technical objectives. Energy systems are deeply embedded in socio-political and economic contexts – both visibly and in more subtle ways (Herkert *et al.*, 2015). Although stakeholder-defined priorities may not directly shape the research questions guiding the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work, they remain closely connected to the outcomes. Acknowledging these links can support modelling teams in presenting and discussing results in ways that are more responsive to stakeholder concerns and better demonstrate the broader relevance of their work.

Recommendations:

- 1.1 Engage stakeholders in dialogue about the purpose, assumptions, and limitations of optimisation-based modelling to align expectations and strengthen mutual understanding.
- 1.2 Acknowledge stakeholder priorities and reflect their relevance when presenting and discussing modelling results to foster responsiveness and ensure impact.

4.2 Perceived power and competence in energy planning

The list of invitees for the stakeholder workshops in both Ethiopia and Zambia was developed through systematic reflection by the two modelling teams at the outset of the project, drawing on their experience, networks, and expertise in national energy planning and policymaking. Workshop participants later shared their views on which actors they consider important in this field. These stakeholder-informed lists of relevant organisations offer an opportunity for the AAU and UNZA teams to revisit and refine their engagement strategies, identify potential gaps, and prioritise new or strengthen existing connections. They may also serve as a starting point for collaboratively exploring

the broader energy planning ecosystem with stakeholders in a more participatory manner. This includes asking critical questions about the current configuration: while the survey captured perceptions of influence among key actors, it did not address whether stakeholders view this distribution as appropriate or believe it should change. Exploring such questions together could provide valuable insights for shaping more inclusive and effective engagement.

In both countries, the ministries of finance rank among the most influential organisations in the field of energy planning. However, they were not represented at either stakeholder workshop and are perceived as having more influence on modelling activities like those under RE-INTEGRATE than genuine interest in being directly involved. This finding is not unexpected: while finance ministries play a critical role in infrastructure financing and the implementation of energy strategies, their core expertise lies outside the energy domain, and their responsibilities span all sectors of the economy. Nonetheless, this raises important questions for both the modelling teams and stakeholder groups. If these ministries are considered key actors but lack both specific competence in energy planning and a strong interest in the modelling work, how can their roles and perspectives be meaningfully acknowledged? One potential approach could involve targeted training sessions on energy planning and participatory modelling for finance and other cross-sectoral ministries (e.g., MoPD, MoMP), to support more informed and constructive engagement in future modelling processes.

At present, academic institutions, development partners, and NGOs are not widely perceived as key actors in energy planning. As an academic institution, AAU, for instance, reports being consulted only at later stages of policy development, without being involved as experts in modelling or energy planning, reinforcing the perception of academia's limited role (AAU-2, 2025). At the same time, modelling assignments in Ethiopia are often awarded to international consultancies through international cooperation projects, suggesting that development partners may, in fact, play a more influential role than stakeholders typically recognise (AAU-2, 2025). While political authority ultimately rests with national governments, development partners and international consultants can significantly shape modelling processes. It is important to acknowledge that models and scenarios are not neutral – they are shaped by subjective decisions that may unintentionally reflect the worldviews of those who design and apply them. This is not a criticism of the support provided by development partners – their expertise is crucial and valuable, especially in countries where energy modelling traditions are still developing. Rather, it highlights an important opportunity to reflect on the importance of stakeholder dialogue at this science-policy interface. Such reflection can support more inclusive modelling processes and ensure that tools and scenarios are better aligned with national priorities and contexts.

While the current role of academia in energy planning may still be limited, we recommend strengthening capacities for model-informed decision-making from the bottom up. In both Ethiopia and Zambia, students are already engaging with energy system models as part of their academic training. Stakeholder dialogues could usefully focus on how these skills can be applied and expanded in practice – such as through partnerships between universities and energy authorities, utilities, development partners, or NGOs to address policy-relevant questions. This approach supports students in building professional networks, understanding the real-world challenges of applying models in decision-making, and refining their skills accordingly. Over time, it can also contribute to the development of stronger national energy modelling ecosystems, reducing dependence on international expertise.

Recommendations:

- 2.1 Collaboratively explore the energy planning landscape with stakeholders to identify missing actors, assess perceived influence, and inform more inclusive engagement strategies.
- 2.2 Offer short and focused training on energy planning and participatory modelling targeted to finance and other cross-sectoral ministries to foster more informed and meaningful engagement.
- 2.3 Foster joint reflection among modelling teams, policymakers, and other stakeholders on the nature of the science-policy interface, including what it means for a responsible use of models and scenarios when actors with different backgrounds and mandates interact.
- 2.4 Promote university-sector partnerships to support student-led modelling work and strengthen national energy planning and modelling ecosystems.

4.3 How respondents perceive the modelling work of RE-INTEGRATE

The survey results suggest that stakeholders in both Ethiopia and Zambia consider the RE-INTEGRATE modelling work as highly relevant to national energy planning. In Ethiopia, this recognition is paired with a strong willingness to engage: 80 % of respondents expressed high levels of interest, and half indicated a desire to be directly involved in the modelling – by far the most intensive form of contribution. In Zambia, interest is similarly high (75 %), but preferred modes of engagement are more varied. While 35% wish to participate directly in the modelling, others prioritise influencing scenario design or simply staying informed. These differences point to varying levels of capacity or readiness to engage, which may reflect institutional constraints, competing priorities, or less familiarity with modelling practices.

Importantly, these patterns must be understood within the broader context of limited resources in the energy planning field. Many stakeholders already face significant demands on their time and institutional capacity, making deep engagement difficult even when interest is genuine. Stakeholder fatigue, particularly where consultation processes lack clear follow-through, further limits participation. In this light, lower levels of expressed involvement should not be mistaken for disinterest but rather understood as a reflection of constrained availability. This underscores the need for flexible, context-sensitive engagement strategies that respect stakeholder time, while still creating meaningful opportunities for collaboration. It also highlights the importance of building long-term institutional capacity to reduce reliance on a small set of overstretched individuals.

Free-text comments from survey respondents further enrich this picture. Participants raised important issues such as gender inclusion, energy affordability for low-income populations, the need for greater alignment with existing modelling efforts, and a desire to participate as model co-developers rather than passive recipients of modelling results. These reflections reinforce the value of inclusive, participatory approaches that go beyond information sharing and actively empower stakeholders to shape the tools and scenarios that may guide future energy policy.

Recommendation:

- 3.1 Establish a consistent and balanced mode of stakeholder engagement – such as periodic email updates and optional virtual touchpoints – to maintain ongoing collaboration instead of focusing on high-intensity, one-off events.

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